

Tri-heteropoly Molybdo-Vanado Tellurate

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Synthesis of sodium, potassium and ammonium salts of heteropoly-5-molybdo-1-vanado tellurate anion $[\text{TeVMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]^{7-}$ are reported. They are characterised by chemical analysis, ir and uv spectra. Thermal stability of the compounds has been examined by DTA and TGA studies. The average molecular weight of sodium 5-molybdo-1-vanadotellurate has been determined by cryoscopy in $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ system and further been confirmed by Weissenberg X ray crystal diffraction method.

THE reportings¹⁻⁵ of mixed heteropoly complexes of molybdenum and tungsten are of much interest. Matjavic and coworkers⁴ synthesised 6-heteropoly anion of general formula $[\text{NiMo}_6-n\text{W}_n\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_6]^{4-}$. Tsigdinos prepared and characterised a number of mixed 12-heteropoly anion of phosphomolybdovanadate⁵ and phosphomolybdoniobates. Heteropoly anion of general formula $[\text{XYW}_{11}\text{O}_{40}\text{H}_2]^{n-}$, where X=Si, Ge, or P and Y= Co^{II} , Co^{III} or Ni^{II} has been prepared⁶. Similar substitution^{7,8} has also been extended in dimeric phosphotungstate anion $[\text{P}_2\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{62}]^{6-}$. Malik⁹ reported that Mn^{II} , Zn^{II} and Fe^{III} can also replace molybdenum in 12-molybdosilicic acid to form a mixed heteropoly anion of the type $[\text{SiYMo}_{11}\text{O}_{40}\text{H}_2]^{n-}$. In view of the above literature survey, we have investigated the replacement of molybdenum by vanadium in the well characterised 6-heteropoly anion¹⁰ $[\text{TeMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$.

Experimental

Sodium 5-molybdo-1-vanadotellurate: Sodium molybdate (10.73 g) dissolved in water (150 ml) and telluric acid (1.84 g) dissolved in water (100 ml), were mixed with each other with constant stirring followed by the addition of glacial acetic acid to maintain the pH at 2.5. To this mixture, freshly prepared sodium metavanadate (0.989 g), dissolved in water (100 ml) was added with stirring keeping the pH constant at 2.5 by acetate buffer solution. It was refluxed for 6 h at 60°, then evaporated and left for crystallisation. After 6 days bright yellow crystals were collected, recrystallised, washed with ethanol and hexane, and then analysed (Found: Na, 10.15; Te, 8.05; V, 2.95; Mo, 30.80; H_2O , 23.76. Calcd. for $\text{Na}_7[\text{TeVMo}_5\text{O}_{24}] \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Na, 10.53; Te, 8.37; V, 3.33; Mo, 31.41; H_2O , 21.20%). The formulation of the compound was based on the views suggested by Evans¹⁰ for heteropoly anion $[\text{TeMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$.

Potassium 5-molybdo-1-vanadotellurate: It was synthesised by refluxing a mixture of aqueous solution of potassium molybdate, potassium metavanadate and telluric acid in 5:1:1 ratio of 2.5-2.6 pH at a controlled temperature of 80° for 8 h. The needle shaped light yellow glassy crystals were collected and analysed (Found: K, 18.32; Te, 9.10; V, 4.70; Mo, 31.85; H_2O , 18.23. Calcd. for $\text{K}_7[\text{TeVMo}_5\text{O}_{24}] \cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$: K, 17.41; Te, 8.23; V, 3.31; Mo, 31.25; H_2O , 12.55%).

Ammonium 5-molybdo-1-vanadotellurate: It was synthesised using ammonium molybdate, ammonium metavanadate and telluric acid. Following the same procedure as above, light orange transparent prismatic crystals were collected after 10 days (Found: N, 6.95; Te, 9.11; V, 4.10; Mo, 33.45; H_2O , 20.65. Calcd. for $(\text{NH}_4)_7[\text{TeVMo}_5\text{O}_{24}] \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$: N, 6.72; Te, 8.78; V, 3.50; Mo, 32.85; H_2O , 19.76%).

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra: The ir spectra of the three compounds were taken on a Perkin Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and the results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—IR SPECTRA OF HETEROPOLY MOLYBDATE

Compd.	ν_{max} cm^{-1}
$\text{Na}_7[\text{TeVMo}_5\text{O}_{24}] \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3 360s, 1 560s, 955m, 935s, 800s, 760m, 960s, 325m
$\text{K}_7[\text{TeVMo}_5\text{O}_{24}] \cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3 300s, 1 625s, 950s, 925m, 805s, 750m, 685s, 330s
$(\text{NH}_4)_7[\text{TeVMo}_5\text{O}_{24}] \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3 420s, 1 620s, 1 405s, 960m, 930s, 800s, 760m, 690s, 325m

s = Strong, m = medium.

The peaks in the region 960-775 cm^{-1} correspond to Mo—O and V—O bridging¹ whereas those

TABLE 2 - THERMAL BEHAVIOUR OF HETEROPOLY MOLYBDATES

Compd.	Temp. (°C) of static heating experiments ^a Number of moles of water/ammonia lost						DTA data ^b (°C)	
	100	150	200	250	300	350	Endo	Exo
Na ₇ [TeVMo ₅ O ₃₄].18H ₂ O	5 Stable	6 Stable	7 Stable	Stable	Unstable	-	30-80 110-140 160-195	270-290
K ₇ [TeVMo ₅ O ₃₄].14H ₂ O	4 Stable	5 Stable	3 Stable	2 Stable	Almost stable	Unstable	30-85 105-130 185-215	320-345
(NH ₄) ₇ [TeVMo ₅ O ₃₄].16H ₂ O	6 Stable	9 Stable	8 Stable	Partly stable	Unstable	-	30-75 110-135 160-185	265-285

^a1-2 g sample used for static heating; stability ascertained by stirring heated sample in 50 ml of water 0.5 h, degree of insolubility of sample taken as a measure of stability. ^bOnly endothermic and exothermic peaks upto the decomposition of compound given; exotherms correspond to complete degradation of heteropoly cage.

in the range 325-330 cm⁻¹ are attributed to Te—O octahedron¹¹. The lattice water absorptions are observed at higher frequency region of 3 460 to 3 300 cm⁻¹, medium frequency range of 1 600 cm⁻¹ and at lower frequency range of 690 cm⁻¹ approximately¹¹.

Electronic spectra: Solution of K₇[TeVMo₅O₃₄].14H₂O were examined spectrophotometrically in various buffer solutions. The compound in 0.1F K₂SO₄-0.2F KHSO₄ buffer solution (pH 2.5) showed the characteristic λ_{max} at 385 nm (ε 2.50 × 10³). This λ_{max} remained almost the same when the spectra of the compound are taken in 0.1F KOOCCH₃ - 0.1F HOOCCCH₃ (pH ~4.5). Thus, it appeared that the compound was stable at pH 2.5-4.5.

Thermal stability: All DTA and TGA experiments were performed under nitrogen at a heating rate of 5° min⁻¹. The thermal behaviour of the heteropoly compounds are given in Table 2. The dehydrated salts exist upto 350° when they are completely decomposed except the K-salt which decomposes near 400°. The endothermic peaks between 30 to 240° correspond to dehydration. Complete degradation of the heteropoly cage at a particular temperature is confirmed by exothermic peaks near that temperature and by chemical analysis, which indicates the existence of mixed oxides of the metal atoms. Insolubility in water, of the heated samples, also confirms the decomposition of the heteropoly salts.

Molecular weight: The molecular weight of Na₇[TeVMo₅O₃₄].18H₂O was determined cryoscopically in Na₂SO₄.10H₂O-Na₂SO₄.H₂O system by the method as has been applied by Thilo and Krüger¹² and recently by Flynn and Pope¹³. The cryoscopic constant was taken¹³ as 1.8 ± .1 kg of water per mole. The derived apparent molecular weight was found to be 1283 ± 250.

X-Ray diffraction: The compound Na₇[TeVMo₅O₃₄].18H₂O was recrystallised from hot water and used for X-ray studies. The unit cell dimensions were determined using rotation and Weissenberg photographs. Crystal data: *M*_{obs} = 1975 against *M*_{calc} = 1958; *a* = 14.62, *b* = 12.48, *c* = 11.52 Å, α = β = γ = 90°, *V* = 2186.13 Å³, *Z* = 2, *D* = 3.0 g cm⁻³.

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